

Domino products from the reaction of 1,3-diaryl-2-propen-1-ones (chalcones) with cyclopentanone

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The simple reaction of chalcones with cyclopentanone in the presence of barium hydroxide furnished complex domino products of the types 4 and 5 along with 1,5-diketones 3. Mechanistic considerations reveal that the bicyclic alcohol 4 was formed by sequential Michael-Michael-aldol reactions involving two moles of chalcone and one mole of cyclopentanone. Whereas, formation of spiro-bicyclic diol 5 involved sequential Michael-1,2-addition-aldol condensation involving one mole of chalcone and two moles of cyclopentanone. Formation of the domino products was found to be critically dependent on electronic fine-tuning in the both the aromatic rings.

Introduction

Generation of complex products from simple starting materials under conditions in which several reactions take place one after another in domino fashion is of continuing interest to organic chemists. Generally such reactions involve multi-component condensation of starting materials. Discovery of domino-reactions on new substrates usually depends on serendipity. 1,3-Diaryl-2-propen-1-ones (chalcones) have been popular substrates for the generation of a variety of heterocyclic products¹. They were also used as precursors for the synthesis of polyphenolic natural products such as flavones, flavanones and flavanols². In addition, there are a few reports in the literature on their utility for the synthesis of carbocyclic products. Recently, Al-Arab and coworkers³ reported the formation of cyclohexanol derivatives from the reaction of chalcones and ethyl cyanoacetate. In this domino reaction, the cyclohexanol derivatives were formed by three-component condensation involving two moles of chalcone and one mole of ethyl cyanoacetate. Noguchi⁴ reported that the condensation of acetophenone and benzaldehyde in biphasic medium in the

presence of PTC results in a cyclohexanol derivative. Formation of cyclohexanol product involves two components of chalcone and one component of acetophenone. We have been interested in the utilization of 1,5-diketones generated by the base-mediated reaction of chalcones and cyclopentanone for the synthesis of 8-azagonanes. We have serendipitously discovered that this reaction affords complex bicyclic and spirocyclic compounds as minor products in addition to expected 1,5-diketones.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of chalcone 1a with cyclopentanone 2 in the presence of barium hydroxide in ethanol at room temperature resulted in the diastereomeric mixture of known⁵ 1,5-diketones 3a (70%, Scheme 1). Further elution of column chromatogram during the purification of the diketones 3a furnished a bicyclic alcohol (4a, 21%), which crystallized out of the fractions (Scheme 1). Elemental analysis and mass spectral data of 4a indicated that the molecular formula was C₃₅H₃₂O₃ (mol. wt. 500). The IR spectrum revealed the presence of hydrogen bonded hydroxy group

1a, 3a, 4a Ar¹ = Ar² = C₆H₅; 1b, 3b Ar¹ = 4-OCH₃-C₆H₄, Ar² = C₆H₅; 1c, 3c Ar¹ = 4-Cl-C₆H₄, Ar² = C₆H₅; 1d, 3d, 4b, 5a Ar¹ = 4-Cl-C₆H₄, Ar² = C₆H₅; 1e, 3e, 5b Ar¹ = 4-Br-C₆H₄, Ar² = C₆H₅; 1f, 3f Ar¹ = 4-NO₂-C₆H₄, Ar² = C₆H₅; 1g, 3g, 4c Ar¹ = C₆H₅, Ar² = 4-OMe-C₆H₄; 1h, 3h Ar¹ = C₆H₅, Ar² = 4-Cl-C₆H₄; 1i, 3i Ar¹ = C₆H₅, Ar² = 4-Cl-C₆H₄; 1j, 3j Ar¹ = C₆H₅, Ar² = 4-NO₂-C₆H₄; 1k, 3k Ar¹ = Ar² = 4-Cl-C₆H₄; 1l, 3l, 4d Ar¹ = 4-Cl-C₆H₄, Ar² = 4-OCH₃-C₆H₄.

Scheme 1. Reagents and conditions : (i) Ba(OH)₂, EtOH, RT.

(3459 cm^{-1}) and two aromatic ketones in which one was involved in hydrogen bond with hydroxyl ($1676, 1647\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum revealed the presence of aromatic and aliphatic protons in the ratio of 5 : 3 indicating that the product was formed by the condensation of two molecules of chalcone and one molecule of cyclopentanone. The $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ spectrum revealed 15 lines out of which 9 were of aliphatic type, 16 of aromatic type and 2 of carbonyl carbons. The DEPT spectrum indicated the presence of 4 quaternary carbons. On the basis of the above spectral data and mechanistic considerations the structure of **4a** was assigned as (6-benzoyl-3 α -hydroxy-5,7-diphenylperhydro-4-indenyl)(phenyl)methanone.

Stereochemistry to various substituents located on the bicyclic alcohol **4a** was assigned on the bases of analysis of $^1\text{H NMR}$, COSY, HETCOR and NOESY spectra. The $\text{C}_4\text{-H}$ appeared as a doublet at $\delta 4.2\text{ ppm}$ with a coupling constant of 12.1 Hz indicating its axial orientation; consequently, the $\text{C}_4\text{-benzoyl}$ group was equatorially oriented. The $\text{C}_5\text{-H}$ appeared as double doublet at $\delta 4.5\text{ ppm}$ with coupling constants 12.1 and 5.2 Hz accounting for axial-axial and axial-equatorial couplings with adjacent hydrogens. This data indicates that the $\text{C}_5\text{-H}$ was axially oriented; consequently, the phenyl group was equatorially oriented. The $\text{C}_6\text{-H}$ appeared as a triplet at $\delta 4.3\text{ ppm}$ with coupling constant of 5.2 Hz indicating equal equatorial-axial coupling to adjacent vicinal hydrogens. Thus $\text{C}_6\text{-H}$ was equatorially oriented; consequently, benzoyl group was axially oriented. The $\text{C}_7\text{-H}$ appeared as a double doublet at $\delta 3.38\text{ ppm}$ with axial-axial and axial-equatorial coupling constants of 12.6 and 5.2 Hz, indicating its axial orientation; consequently, the $\text{C}_7\text{-phenyl}$ was equatorially oriented. These data also

indicate that the bridgehead $\text{C}_{7a}\text{-H}$ was axially oriented, which appeared as broad double doublet at $\delta 2.9\text{ ppm}$. The *trans* stereochemistry to the ring junction was assigned on the basis of strong hydrogen bonding interactions between $\text{C}_{3a}\text{-hydroxyl}$ group and adjacent $\text{C}_4\text{-benzoyl}$ group indicating their *syn* orientation. The energy-minimized structure was generated in MM2 mode (minimum energy = 19.99 kcal; Fig. 1), which clearly shows hydrogen-bonding inter-

Fig. 1. Energy minimized structure of (6-benzoyl-3 α -hydroxy-5,7-diphenylperhydro-4-indenyl)(phenyl)methanone **4a**

action between the $\text{C}_{3a}\text{-hydroxy}$ group and carbonyl oxygen of the adjacent $\text{C}_4\text{-benzoyl}$ group (hydrogen bond distance = 184.8 pm). Theoretical coupling constants generated from minimum energy conformation of **4a** also agreed well with the experimentally observed values⁶.

The mechanism for the formation of **4a** is given in Scheme 2. The conjugate addition (Michael reaction) of the anion generated from cyclopentanone to chalcone leads to

Scheme 2

enolate anion intermediate **6**, which reacts with one more molecule of chalcone in Michael fashion to generate intermediate enolate anion **7**. The intermediate **7** undergoes intramolecular aldol condensation to furnish the bicyclic alcohol **4a**. This unique reaction generated stereochemically well-defined single diastereomer **4a** bearing 6 consecutive chiral centers, out of possible 32 pairs of diastereomers. The axial orientation of C₆-benzoyl group instead of equatorial orientation in **4a** during its formation appears to be a deviation from normal expectations. The axial-orientation of C₆-benzoyl group is likely to relieve severe steric congestion with adjacent equatorially oriented bulky phenyl rings in C₅- and C₇-positions.

We have made attempts to improve the yield of the bicyclic alcohol **4a** by changing the solvent and as well as the base used in the reaction. We have conducted this multi-component condensation reaction in a selection of solvents like methanol, *t*-butanol, THF or dichloromethane. However, best yield of **4a** was obtained in ethanol medium. A variety of bases such as potassium hydroxide in ethanol, sodium hydroxide in ethanol, sodium methoxide in methanol or in dry diethyl ether, and sodium hydride in THF were tried for promoting the multi-component condensation reaction. Surprisingly, in all the cases the desired bicyclic alcohol was either obtained in minute quantities (less than 3% yield) or did not form at all. Interestingly, when the reaction was conducted in biphasic medium under the conditions described by Nogouch⁴ only conjugate addition product **3a** was obtained in 96% yield. Thus, barium hydroxide and ethanol appeared to be unique in propelling the reaction towards domino pathways.

Next, we studied the effect of electron-donating and withdrawing substituents on the phenyl rings towards the formation of bicyclic alcohol of the type **4**. When the chalcones having electron-donating 4-methoxy (**1b**) and 4-methyl (**1c**) groups in the aryl ring Ar¹ ring were employed as substrates, the reaction was sluggish and it furnished only conjugate addition products **3b-c**. However, when the chalcone **1d** having electron-withdrawing 4-chloro substituent was used as substrate, the reaction furnished diastereomeric mixture of conjugate addition products **3d**, bicyclic alcohol **4b** and a novel spiro-bicyclic diol **5a** (Scheme 1). The structure of the bicyclic alcohol **4b** was confirmed on the basis of ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra, which were remarkably similar to the parent bicyclic alcohol **4a**. Furthermore, 2D-NMR spectral data (COSY, HETCOR, NOESY) were also in conformity with the proposed structure for **4b**.

The new compound **5a**, a colorless crystalline solid, m.p.

225°, obtained in 3% yield, was found to have molecular formula C₂₅H₂₇ClO₃ from analytical and mass spectral data. The IR spectrum revealed the presence of a hydrogen bonded hydroxyl group (3192) and a carbonyl group (1716 cm⁻¹). The ¹H NMR spectrum revealed the presence of aromatic and aliphatic protons in the ratio 1 : 2, which indicated that the product was formed from two units of cyclopentanone and one unit of chalcone. The two hydroxy groups (hydrogen exchangeable with deuterium in D₂O) were observed as broad singlets at δ 3.3 and 3.98 ppm. The absence of characteristic signals in the IR spectrum for an aromatic carbonyl group (~1660 cm⁻¹) and signals in the ¹H NMR at δ 3.5–4.5 ppm suggested the involvement of the aromatic carbonyl group of the chalcone in the bond formation. The ¹H NMR spectrum revealed a double doublet at δ 3.43 ppm (*J* 13.5, 4.0 Hz) for C₅-H_{ax} indicating the presence of this tertiary benzylic hydrogen next to C₆' methylene group. At δ 3.00 ppm a double doublet for C₆'-H_{ax} with *J* 14, 13.5 Hz was observed. The ¹H-¹H COSY spectrum revealed the connectivity between the double doublets located at δ 3.43 and 3.00 ppm. The COSY spectrum also revealed the connectivity between the peak at δ 3.00 ppm and the double doublet located at δ 1.76 ppm assignable to C₆'-H_{eq}. Generally axially oriented hydrogen in cyclohexane appears upfield compared to the equatorial one due to shielding effect. However, in the present case, the appearance of C₆'-axial hydrogen downfield can be assigned to anisotropic effect of the sterically proximate carbonyl group. The ¹H NMR revealed a double doublet at δ 2.95 ppm (*J* 13, 7.5 Hz) attributable to axially oriented C₇'_a-H. The ¹³C NMR showed the presence of 12 aliphatic type carbons, 8 aromatic carbons and 1 carbonyl carbon. The carbonyl carbon was observed at 223.37 ppm indicating it to be a cyclopentanone type. The two carbons attached to hydroxyl group were observed at δ 76.5 and 83.94 ppm. Analysis of the DEPT spectrum indicated the presence of seven methylene carbons, two methine carbons and three quaternary carbons in addition to one carbonyl carbon. Based upon the spectral data, the structure of the novel product **5a** formed in the reaction was proposed as 7'-(4-chlorophenyl)-3a',7'-dihydroxy-5'-phenylspiro[cyclopentane-1,4'-perhydroindene]-2-one. The HETCOR and NOESY spectra of **5a** confirmed the proposed structure.

The stereochemistry of the various substituents in **5a** was assigned on the basis of coupling constants as revealed in high-resolution ¹H NMR spectrum. As expected from the structure of **5a** C₅' proton appeared as double doublet at δ 3.43 with coupling constants of 13.5 and 4.0 Hz. The magnitude of the coupling constants indicated that C₅ proton is having axial-axial coupling with C₆'-H axial and

axial-equatorial coupling with C₆-H equatorial. Thus the C₅-phenyl group was equatorially oriented and consequently the C₅-H is axially oriented. The two protons on C₆ appeared as double doublets at δ 3 and 1.76. As discussed earlier, hydrogen-bonding interaction between the two OH groups at C₇ and C_{3a} was indicated by the IR spectrum. This arrangement requires both the C_{3a}-OH and C₇-OH to be in axial position. By deduction the C₇ chlorophenyl group can be taken as located in equatorial orientation. The stereochemistry of the ring junction being *trans* was indicated by the coupling constants of C_{7a}-H (δ 2.95, dd, *J* 13, 7.5 Hz). Final confirmation of the proposed structure of **5a** was obtained by X-ray analysis on a thin needle shaped crystalline sample obtained by recrystallization from dichloromethane hexane solvent mixtures (ORTEP diagram with crystallographic numbering, Fig. 2). The crystal structure analysis revealed a short hydrogen bond of length 266 pm between O₁ and symmetry-related O₂. The structure appears to be stabilized mainly by van der Waals interactions. The minimum energy conformation of this molecule was generated using molecular mechanics calculation using MMXE mode (MMXE = 39.78 kcal; Fig. 3), which clearly shows hydrogen bonding interactions between two hydroxyl groups and the cyclopentanone carbonyl oxygen.

A possible mechanism for the formation of the spiro-bicyclic diol **5a** is given in Scheme 3. The 1,5-diketone **3d** formed via the Michael addition of anion generated from cyclopentanone reacts with one more unit of cyclopentanone in 1,2 fashion to furnish the diketone alcohol **8**. Intramolecular aldol condensation of **8** results in spiro-bicyclic diol **5a**. The involvement of two hydroxy groups in intramolecular hydrogen bonding may be the driving force for the formation of the final product.

We attempted to increase the yield of spiro-diol **5a** by

Scheme 3

Fig. 2. ORTEP diagram of 7'-(4-chlorophenyl)-3a',7'-dihydroxy-5'-phenylspiro[cyclopentane-1,4'-perhydroindene]-2-one **5a** (with crystallographic numbering).

Fig. 3. Energy minimized structure of 7'-(4-chlorophenyl)-3a',7'-dihydroxy-5'-phenylspiro[cyclopentane-1,4'-perhydroindene]-2-one **5a**.

changing various reaction conditions, such as concentration, solvent, base etc. Change of solvent from absolute alcohol to acetonitrile, as well as sonication also did not increase the yield of the desired product. A variation in the reaction conditions, such as heating to reflux or prolonged stirring (36 h) also did not improve the yield of **5a**. According to the proposed mechanism, the formation of spirodiol was due to the addition of two cyclopentanone moieties to one chalcone moiety. Hence, 1,5-diketone **3d** and cyclopentanone **2** were allowed to react (Scheme 4). But instead of the spiro-

Scheme 4. Reagents and conditions : (i) Ba(OH)₂, EtOH, RT, 12 h, 12%.

diol **5a**, the reaction furnished the bicyclic alcohol **4b** as an isolable product. The formation of **4b** in this reaction indicates the generation of chalcone **1d** under the reaction conditions which then adds to 1,5-diketone **3d** to furnish the bicyclic alcohol **5a**.

The reaction of chalcone **1e** having electron-withdrawing bromo substituent in Ar¹ ring with cyclopentanone furnished the diastereomeric mixture of diketones **3e** along with spirobicyclic diol **5b** in 5% yield (Scheme 1). The structure of **5b** was assigned on the basis of spectral data (IR, ¹H, ¹³C NMR, MS) and on comparison with the data for **5a**. Surprisingly this reaction did not furnish any bicyclic alcohol of the type **4**.

Interestingly, the reaction of chalcone **1f** having strongly electron-withdrawing 4-nitro group resulted in only in the diastereomeric mixture of 1,5-diketones **3f**. There was no trace of bicyclic alcohols of the type **4** or **5** in the product mixture.

Next we studied the barium hydroxide mediated reaction of chalcones having electron donating (**1g-h**) and withdrawing groups (**1i-j**) in Ar² ring with cyclopentanone. The reaction of chalcone **1g** having strongly electron-donating OMe group in Ar² ring furnished bicyclic alcohol **4c** along with the diastereomeric mixture of diketones **4g**. The spectral data of bicyclic alcohol **4c** (IR, ¹H, ¹³C NMR, COSY, HETCOR, NOESY) were remarkably similar to **4a** and **4b**. The reaction of chalcones **1h-j** having moderately electron-donating methyl group, electron-withdrawing Cl or nitro group resulted only in diketones **3h-j**. The reaction of

chalcone **1k** having electron-withdrawing 4-chloro substituent in Ar¹ and Ar² rings also resulted in only diketone **3k**. However, the reaction of chalcone **1l** having electron-withdrawing Cl in Ar¹ and electron-donating OMe in Ar² rings resulted in diketones **3l** and bicyclic alcohol **4d** (10%). Unfortunately, the bicyclic alcohol **4d** was obtained only as a mixture of stereoisomers, which could not be separated by column chromatography or by fractional crystallization. Location of electron-withdrawing substituent on Ar¹ ring and electron-donating substituent on Ar² ring makes the

chalcone a push-pull system. These substituents also promote conjugate addition characteristics of the system. Our studies show that the presence of moderately electron-withdrawing substituents on Ar¹ ring and strongly electron-donating substituents on Ar² ring drive the initial conjugate addition intermediates towards second conjugate addition leading to the formation of domino products. Furthermore, our studies also revealed that the formation of the domino products is critically dependent on reaction conditions such as choice of base and solvent.

In conclusion, we have shown in this study that the reaction of chalcones with cyclopentanone in the presence of barium hydroxide in ethanol medium furnishes novel and interesting bicyclic alcohols of the type **4** or spiro-bicyclic diols of the type **5** depending on the electronic fine-tuning of the aryl rings. The structure and stereochemistry of the different substituents were assigned on the basis of analysis of the high resolution NMR data and 2D NMR spectral data. In the case of spiro-bicyclic diol **5a**, the structure was confirmed on the basis of X-ray structure analysis.

Experimental

Hexanes/ethyl acetate (9 : 1) solvent mixture for TLC (TLC silica gel, Qualigens or TLC neutral alumina, SRL, India) was used to monitor the progress of the reactions. The column chromatography was performed on silica gel (100–200 mesh, Acme Synthetic Chemicals) using increasing percentage of ethyl acetate in hexane. All the solvents were distilled before use. Barium hydroxide (B.D.H.) was

activated by heating at 120° for 1 h and cooled to room temperature (30°) in a desiccator. The chalcones were prepared according to literature procedures⁷. Melting points were noted using a Gallenkamp apparatus. IR spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Jasco FTIR spectrophotometer, ¹H, ¹³C and 2D NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on Bruker 500 MHz, JEOL 400 MHz, Varian 300 MHz or Bruker 200 MHz spectrometers with internal TMS as reference and mass spectra on a GEOL GC/MS low-resolution instrument.

Representative procedure for the reaction of cyclopentanone with chalcones in the presence of barium hydroxide. Condensation of 1,3-diphenyl-2-propen-1-one 1a with cyclopentanone 2 : To a stirred suspension of activated barium hydroxide (0.400 g, 2 mmol) in anhydrous ethanol (10 ml), cyclopentanone (0.840 g, 10 mmol) was added dropwise at RT and stirring continued for 10 min. 1,3-Diphenyl-2-propen-1-one (**1a**; 2.08 g, 10 mmol) was added portionwise during 10 min and the suspension was stirred for 12 h for completion of the reaction (TLC) by which time it turned reddish-brown. The reaction mixture was filtered through celite and the clear filtrate was diluted with water (50 ml) and dichloromethane (50 ml). The organic layer was washed with water (2 × 25 ml) and brine solution (25 ml). Removal of solvent under reduced pressure resulted in viscous mass, which on column chromatography using silica gel (100–200 mesh) with hexane/ethyl acetate solution as eluent furnished **3a** and **4a** in 91% combined yield. *2-(3-Oxo-1,3-diphenylpropyl)cyclopentanone 3a* (70%, m.p. 67°, ν_{\max} (KBr) 3060, 2910, 1730, 1680, 1450, 1200 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR (60 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.10–2.10 (5H, m), 2.3–3.15 (2H, m), 3.1–3.85 (3H, m), 7.1–8.0 (10H, m). *(6-Benzoyl-3a-hydroxy-5,7-diphenylperhydro-4-indenyl)(phenyl)methanone 4a* (21%), m.p. 206° (Found : C, 83.91; H, 6.48. C₃₅H₃₂O₃ calcd. for : C, 83.97; H, 6.44%), ν_{\max} (KBr) 3458, 3061, 3030, 2953, 2851, 1676, 1647, 1595, 1577, 1494, 1446, 1373, 1304, 1250 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR (270 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.80 (2H, d, *J* 12.0 Hz), 7.0–7.5 (18H, m), 4.7 (1H, s), 4.3 (1H, t, *J* 5.2 Hz), 4.2 (1H, d, *J* 12.1 Hz), 4.10 (1H, dd, *J* 12.0, 4.5 Hz), 3.38 (1H, dd, *J* 12.6, 5.2 Hz), ¹³C NMR (50 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 212.21, 204.92, 144.51, 140.00, 139.90, 136.10, 132.62, 132.43, 128.81, 128.60, 128.30, 128.20, 128.10, 127.80, 127.41, 126.74, 126.70, 80.90, 55.15, 48.30, 42.50, 33.40, 23.90 ppm; MS (EI) 500 (M⁺), 402, 376, 360, 327, 292, 274, 246, 209, 173, 131, 105 (100%), 77.

Reaction of 4-methoxychalcone 1b with cyclopentanone : Following the general procedure described above, the reaction of (*E*)-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (**1b**; 1.19 g, 5 mmol) and cyclopentanone (**2**; 460 mg, 5.5 mmol) in the presence of freshly activated

barium hydroxide (400 mg, 2 mmol) in absolute alcohol (5 ml) for 12 h at RT resulted in the inseparable mixture of diastereomeric 1,5-diketones as gummy liquid. The *R_f* value was comparable with other 1,5-diketones and IR spectrum indicated the formation of 1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3-(2-oxocyclopentyl)-3-phenyl-1-propanone **3b**.

Reaction of 4-methylchalcone 1c with cyclopentanone : Following the general procedure described above, the reaction of (*E*)-1-(4-methylphenyl)-3-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (**1c**; 1.11 g, 5 mmol) and cyclopentanone (**2**; 462 mg, 5.5 mmol) in the presence of freshly activated barium hydroxide (200 mg) in absolute alcohol (5 ml) for 12 h at RT resulted in the inseparable mixture of diastereomeric 1,5-diketones as gummy liquid. The *R_f* value was comparable with other 1,5-diketones and IR spectrum indicated the formation of 1-(4-methylphenyl)-3-(2-oxocyclopentyl)-3-phenyl-1-propanone **3c**.

Reaction of 4-chlorochalcone 1d with cyclopentanone : Following the general procedure described above, the reaction of (*E*)-1-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (**1d**; 1.21 g, 5 mmol) and cyclopentanone (**2**; 462 mg, 5.5 mmol) in the presence of freshly activated barium hydroxide (200 mg) in absolute alcohol (5 ml) for 12 h at RT resulted in three products which were separated by column chromatography using silica gel (100–200 mesh) with hexane/ethyl acetate solutions as eluent (98 : 2 to 80 : 20).

1-(4-Chlorophenyl)-3-(2-oxocyclopentyl)-3-phenyl-1-propanone 3d : Single diastereomer was obtained by fractional crystallization (49%), m.p. 108°, *R_f* 0.6; ν_{\max} (KBr) 2961, 1730, 1680, 1589, 1450, 1400, 1215, 1093, 993, 815, 698, 526 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.90 (2H, dd, *J* 15, 5 Hz), 7.30–7.50 (2H, m), 7.10–7.30 (5H, m Aro H), 3.90 (1H, dd, *J* 17.5, 7.5 Hz), 3.50–3.70 (1H, m), 3.30 (1H, ddd, *J* 20, 15, 5 Hz), 2.30–2.50 (1H, m), 2.00–2.30 (2H, m), 1.60–2.00 (4H, m); ¹³C NMR (50 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 221.0, 197.9, 142.1, 139.4, 135.4, 129.6, 128.9, 128.5, 128.4, 126.8, 53.0, 41.2, 40.9, 39.7, 27.1, 20.6 ppm.

6-(4-Chlorobenzoyl)-3a-hydroxy-5,7-diphenylperhydro-4-indenylchlorophenylmethanone 4b : Yield 7%, m.p. 221°, *R_f* 0.45; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3500, 3000, 1660, 1590, 1400, 1090, 700 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.60 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.30 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 7.20–7.60 (2H, m), 7.14–7.20 (2H, m), 7.10–7.12 (5H, m), 7.00–7.05 (5H, m), 4.60 (1H, s), 4.21 (1H, t, *J* 4.88 Hz), 4.14 (1H, d, *J* 4.88 Hz), 4.04 (1H, dd, *J* 12, 5 Hz), 3.35 (1H, dd, *J* 13.5, 5.86 Hz), 2.9 (1H, br dd), 1.94–2.06 (1H, m), 1.70–1.80 (1H, m), 1.60–1.70 (1H, m), 1.45–1.60 (1H, m), 1.38–1.45 (1H, m), 0.94–1.10 (1H, m); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 203.8, 201.4, 144.3, 139.73, 139.2, 139.1, 137.9, 136.2,

129.5, 129.2, 128.9, 128.7, 128.5, 128.4, 128.2, 127.3, 127.0, 126.1, 80.9, 55.3, 55.2, 48.6, 48.2, 43.4, 42.4, 33.5, 24.0 ppm; HRMS (M^+) m/z calcd. for $C_{35}H_{30}Cl_2O_3$ 568.1572, obsd. 568.1574.

7'-(4-Chlorophenyl)-3a',7'-dihydroxy-5'-phenylspiro[cyclopentane-1,4'-perhydroindene]-2-one 5a : Yield 3%, m.p. 225°; R_f 0.26; ν_{max} (KBr) 3192, 2961, 1716, 1493, 1452, 1404, 1323, 1252, 1186, 1157, 1093, 1057, 1012, 960, 883, 812, 763, 704, 574, 547, 497 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.51 (2H, dd, J 8, 1.5 Hz), 7.30 (2H, dd, J 8, 1.5 Hz), 7.20 (3H, m), 7.18 (2H, dm, J 8, 1.5 Hz), 3.98 (1H, br s), 3.43 (1H, dd, J 13.5, 4 Hz), 3.30 (1H, br s), 3.0 (1H, dd, J 14, 13.5 Hz), 2.95 (1H, dd, J 13, 7.5 Hz), 2.32 (1H, dt, J 14, 8.5 Hz), 2.07 (1H, ddd, J 15, 7.5, 4.5 Hz), 1.98 (2H, ddd, J 17.5, 8.5, 5 Hz), 1.76 (1H, dd, J 14, 4 Hz), 1.70–1.75 (2H, m), 1.50–1.60 (2H, m), 1.22–1.30 (2H, m), 0.62–0.72 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 223.4, 145.6, 141.2, 132.6, 128.9, 128.5, 128.4, 127.2, 126.0, 83.9, 76.5, 58.9, 47.4, 45.3, 44.3, 42.5, 35.4, 32.7, 20.9, 19.4 and 18.9 ppm; HRMS (M^+) m/z calcd. for $C_{25}H_{27}ClO_3$ 410.1649, obsd. 410.1647.

Reaction of 4-bromochalcone 1e with cyclopentanone 2 : Following the general procedure described above, the reaction of (*E*)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (**1e**; 1.43 g, 5 mmol) and cyclopentanone **2** (462 mg, 5.5 mmol) in the presence of freshly activated barium hydroxide (200 mg) in absolute alcohol (5 ml) for 12 h at RT resulted in two products which were separated by column chromatography using silica gel (100–200 mesh) with hexane/ethyl acetate solutions as eluent (98 : 2 to 80 : 20).

1-(4-Bromophenyl)-3-(2-oxocyclopentyl)-3-phenyl-1-propanone 3e : Single diastereomer was crystallized out of column fractions (48%), m.p. 124°; R_f 0.55; ν_{max} (KBr) 2961, 1730, 1680, 1583, 1493, 1448, 1398, 1259, 1215, 1151, 1070, 993, 812, 727, 698, 561 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.80 (2H, dd, J 17.5, 7.5 Hz), 7.60 (2H, d, J 7.5 Hz), 7.10–7.40 (5H, m), 3.90 (1H, dd, J 15, 5 Hz), 3.60–3.75 (1H, m), 3.20–3.50 (1H, dd, J 15, 5 Hz), 2.40–2.60 (1H, m), 2.00–2.30 (2H, m), 1.60–2.00 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR (50 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 220.6, 198.1, 142.0, 135.7, 131.8, 129.7, 128.5, 128.4, 128.2, 126.8, 52.9, 41.1, 40.8, 39.7, 27.1, 20.5 ppm.

7'-(4-Bromophenyl)-3a',7'-dihydroxy-5'-phenylspiro[cyclopentane-1,4'-perhydroindene]-2-one 5b : Yield 5%, m.p. 202; R_f 0.28; ν_{max} (KBr) 3300, 2900, 1800, 1720, 1500, 1400, 1100, 960, 900, 840, 780, 710, 550 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.43–7.49 (4H, m), 7.17–7.26 (5H, m), 3.91 (1H, s), 3.43 (1H, dd, J 13, 3 Hz), 3.27 (1H, s), 2.7 (1H, dt, J 12, 7 Hz), 2.30 (1H, dt, J 14, 8 Hz), 2.09

(1H, ddd, J 20, 12, 6 Hz), 1.93 (2H, ddd, J 18, 9, 5, Hz), 1.75–1.80 (2H, m), 1.69–1.74 (2H, m), 1.51–1.61 (2H, m), 1.21–1.27 (2H, m), 0.63–0.70 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (50 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 223.4, 146.1, 141.2, 131.2, 128.9, 128.5, 127.2, 126.4, 120.7, 83.9, 76.5, 58.9, 47.3, 45.3, 44.2, 42.5, 35.4, 32.7, 20.8, 19.4, 18.6 ppm; HRMS (M^+) m/z calcd. for $C_{25}H_{27}BrO_3$ 454.1144, obsd. 454.1141.

Reaction of 4-nitrochalcone 1f with cyclopentanone 2 : Following the general procedure described above, the reaction of (*E*)-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (**1f**; 1.26 g, 5 mmol) and cyclopentanone **2** (462 mg, 5.5 mmol) in the presence of freshly activated barium hydroxide (200 mg) in absolute alcohol (5 ml) for 12 h at RT resulted in diastereomeric mixture of 1,5-diketones (TLC) which were purified by column chromatography using silica gel (100–200 mesh) with hexane/ethyl acetate solutions as eluent (98 : 2 to 80 : 20).

1-(4-Nitrophenyl)-3-(2-oxocyclopentyl)-3-phenyl-1-propanone 3f : Major diastereomer was isolated by fractional crystallization (66%), m.p. 100–102°; R_f 0.45; ν_{max} (KBr) 3113, 2932, 1728, 1685, 1602, 1521, 1402, 1346, 1201, 1153, 995, 854, 746, 702, 513 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 8.15 (2H, dd, J 16, 5 Hz), 7.40–7.60 (2H, m), 7.10–7.40 (5H, m), 4.00 (1H, dd, J 12, 6 Hz), 3.50–3.70 (1H, m), 3.35 (1H, ddd, J 20, 16, 6 Hz), 2.40–2.60 (1H, m), 2.10–2.30 (2H, m), 1.50–2.00 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR (50 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 219.9, 197.2, 150.2, 142.4, 141.7, 129.4, 129.0, 128.6, 126.9, 123.8, 52.7, 43.9, 41.3, 38.8, 28.6, 20.2 ppm.

Reaction of 4'-methoxychalcone 1g with cyclopentanone 2 : Following the general procedure, the reaction of (*E*)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (**1g**; 1.19 g, 5 mmol) and cyclopentanone **2** (462 mg, 5.5 mmol) in the presence of freshly activated barium hydroxide (200 mg) in absolute alcohol (5 ml) for 12 h at RT resulted in diastereomeric mixture of 1,5-diketones (TLC) which were purified by column chromatography using silica gel (100–200 mesh) with hexane/ethyl acetate solutions as eluent (98 : 2 to 85 : 15).

2-[1-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-3-oxo-3-phenylpropyl]-1-cyclopentanone 3g : Major diastereomer was crystallized out of column fractions (70%), R_f 0.37; ν_{max} (KBr) 3433, 3059, 2957, 2932, 1730, 1684, 1610, 1512, 1448, 1249, 1180, 1033, 833, 734 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.9 (2H, q, J 9 Hz), 7.3–7.5 (3H, m), 7.0–7.2 (2H, m), 6.7–6.8 (2H, m), 3.7 (3H, s), 3.2–3.5 (2H, m), 2.2–2.5 (3H, m), 2.0 (1H, s), 1.1–1.3 (3H, m), 0.7–0.95 (1H, m); ^{13}C NMR (50 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 220.9, 199.9, 158.5, 137.5, 134.5, 132.6, 129.8, 129.2, 128.4, 114.1, 54.9, 53.5, 39.5,

39.3, 24.9, 20.2 ppm.

6-Benzoyl-3a-hydroxy-5,7-di(4-methoxyphenyl)-perhydro-4-indenyl-1-phenylmethanone 4c : Yield 2%, m.p. 168°, R_f 0.31; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3400, 2940, 1650, 1500, 1450, 1240, 1170, 1020, 970, 820, 710, 680 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.7 (2H, dt, J 8, 1.1 Hz), 7.5 (1H, tt, J 9.3, 1.2 Hz), 7.3 (2H, tm, J 9.2 Hz), 7.2–7.3 (1H, tt, J 9, 1.2 Hz), 7.2 (2H, dt, J 9.3, 2.1 Hz), 7.1 (2H, dt, J 8.7, 2 Hz), 6.7 (2H, dt, J 8.7, 1.8 Hz), 4.2 (1H, t, J 5.3 Hz), 4.1 (1H, d, J 12.3 Hz), 4.0 (1H, dd, J 12.3, 5.3 Hz), 3.6 (3H, s), 3.6 (3H, s), 2.9–3.0 (1H, ddd, J 12.3, 9.3, 7.8 Hz), 1.9–2.0 (1H, m), 1.7–1.8 (1H, m), 1.6–1.7 (1H, m), 1.5–1.6 (1H, m), 1.4–1.5 (1H, m), 0.9–1.1 (1H, m); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (95 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 205.2, 203.1, 158.0, 139.9, 132.5, 132.4, 132.3, 129.5, 128.4, 114.1, 80.9, 48.6, 47.7, 42.5, 42.3, 33.8, 23.9 ppm.

Reaction of 4'-methylchalcone 1h with cyclopentanone 2 : Following the general procedure, the reaction of (*E*)-3-(4-methylphenyl)-1-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (**1h**; 1.11 g, 5 mmol) and cyclopentanone **2** (462 mg, 5.5 mmol) in the presence of freshly activated barium hydroxide (200 mg) in absolute alcohol (5 ml) for 12 h at RT resulted in diastereomeric mixture of 1,5-diketones (TLC) which were purified by column chromatography using silica gel (100–200 mesh) with hexane/ethyl acetate solutions as eluent (98 : 2 to 85 : 15).

2-[1-(4-Methylphenyl)-3-oxo-3-phenylpropyl]-1-cyclopentanone 3h : Yield 40%, R_f 0.5; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3232, 3057, 2966, 1720, 1685, 1597, 1514, 1488, 1265, 1157, 879, 819, 738, 700 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (200 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.8–8 (2H, m, J 8.2 Hz), 7.6 (2H, d, J 8 Hz), 7.2–7.5 (7H, m), 7–7.2 (6H, m), 3.7–3.8 (1H, m), 3.4–3.5 (2H, dd, J 5, 4 Hz), 3–3.1 (2H, m), 2.3 (3H, s), 2.2–2.4 (3H, m), 1.7–2 (4H, m), 1.5–1.6 (6H, m), 1.3 (4H, q, J 12.8 Hz), 0.6–0.8 (1H, m) ppm.

Reaction of 4'-chlorochalcone 1i with cyclopentanone 2 : Following the general procedure, the reaction of (*E*)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (**1i**; 1.21 g, 5 mmol) and cyclopentanone **2** (462 mg, 5.5 mmol) in the presence of freshly activated barium hydroxide (200 mg) in absolute alcohol (5 ml) for 12 h at RT resulted in diastereomeric mixture of 1,5-diketones (TLC) which were purified by column chromatography using silica gel (100–200 mesh) with hexane/ethyl acetate solutions as eluent (98 : 2 to 85 : 15).

2-[1-(4-Chlorophenyl)-3-oxo-3-phenylpropyl]-1-cyclopentanone 3i : Mixture of diastereomers (76%), m.p. 157°; R_f 0.42; ν_{\max} (neat) 3408, 3063, 2964, 1722, 1676, 1649, 1595, 1491, 1221, 819, 686, 561 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$

(200 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.6–7.9 (2H, dd, J 8.0, 10.0 Hz), 7.4–7.5 (2H, m), 7.1–7.3 (3H, m), 7–7.1 (7H, m), 4.5 (1H, s), 4.0–4.2 (2H, m), 3.7–3.8 (3H, dd, J 6, 8 Hz), 3.4–3.5 (1H, q), 3.2–3.5 (2H, m), 2.9 (1H, q, J 14 Hz), 2.5 (1H, q, J 10 Hz), 1.9–2.1 (2H, m), 1.7 (1H, m), 1.4–1.6 (4H, m), 0.9–1.1 (1H, m) ppm.

Reaction of 4'-nitrochalcone 1j with cyclopentanone 2 : Following the general procedure, the reaction of (*E*)-3-(4-nitrophenyl)-1-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (**1j**; 1.265 g, 5 mmol) and cyclopentanone **2** (462 mg, 5.5 mmol) in the presence of freshly activated barium hydroxide (200 mg) in absolute alcohol (5 ml) for 12 h at RT resulted in diastereomeric mixture of 1,5-diketones (TLC) which were purified by column chromatography using silica gel (100–200 mesh) with hexane/ethyl acetate solutions as eluent (98 : 2 to 80 : 15).

2-[1-(4-Nitrophenyl)-3-oxo-3-phenylpropyl]-1-cyclopentanone 3j : Major diastereomer was crystallized out of the column fractions (38%); R_f 0.4; ν_{\max} (KBr) 2964, 1734, 1684, 1599, 1520, 1346, 858 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (200 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.0 (4H, d, J 9 Hz), 7.9 (4H, d, J 4 Hz), 7.3–7.4 (10H, m), 3.7–4.0 (5H, m), 3.4–3.6 (5H, m), 2.1–2.3 (2H, dd, J 10, 12 Hz), 1.9 (2H, q, J 6 Hz), 0.8 (1H, t, J 15 Hz); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (50 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 218.7, 197.7, 150.8, 136.7, 133.2, 129.2, 128.6, 123.4, 53.6, 42.3, 40.3, 38.9, 26.8, 20.1 ppm.

Reaction of 4,4'-dichlorochalcone 1k with cyclopentanone 2 : Following the general procedure, the reaction of (*E*)-1,3-dichlorophenyl-2-propen-1-one (**1k**; 1.38 g, 5 mmol) and cyclopentanone **2** (462 mg, 5.5 mmol) in the presence of freshly activated barium hydroxide (200 mg) in absolute alcohol (5 ml) for 12 h at RT resulted in diastereomeric mixture of 1,5-diketones **3k** (TLC) which were purified by column chromatography using silica gel (100–200 mesh) with hexane/ethyl acetate solutions as eluent (98 : 2 to 85 : 15).

1,3-Di(4-chlorophenyl)-3-(2-oxocyclopentyl)-1-propanone 3k : Major diastereomer was crystallized out of column fractions (64%), m.p. 150°; R_f 0.5; ν_{\max} (KBr) 2928, 2847, 1714, 1685, 1489, 1400, 1356, 1155, 1091, 1012, 831, 760, 592, 526, 420 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (200 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.85 (2H, d, J 9 Hz), 7.4 (2H, d, J 9.1 Hz), 7.2 (2H, d, J 9 Hz), 7.1 (2H, d, J 9 Hz), 3.8–3.9 (2H, dd, J 16, 6 Hz), 3.7 (2H, q, J 12 Hz), 3.3 (2H, dd, J 16, 9.2 Hz), 2.4 (1H, q, J 14 Hz), 1.6–1.8 (2H, m), 1.2–1.5 (2H, m); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (50 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 218, 196.9, 140.6, 139.4, 135.2, 134.8, 129.5, 128.9, 128.6, 53.4, 42.9, 40.8, 26.9, 25.5 ppm.

Reaction of 4-chloro-4'-methoxychalcone 1l with cyclopentanone 2 : Following the general procedure, the

reaction of (*E*)-1-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-one (**1**; 1.36 g, 5 mmol) and cyclopentanone **2** (462 mg, 5.5 mmol) in the presence of freshly activated barium hydroxide (200 mg) in absolute alcohol (5 ml) for 12 h at RT resulted in diastereomeric mixture of 1,5-diketones **3** and bicyclic alcohol **4** (TLC) which were purified by column chromatography using silica gel (100–200 mesh) with hexane/ethyl acetate solutions as eluent (98 : 2 to 85 : 15).

1-(4-Chlorophenyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3-(2-oxocyclopentyl)-1-propanone 3 : Mixture of diastereomers (60%), R_f 0.5; ν_{\max} (neat) 2960, 1720, 1680, 1590, 1510, 1400, 1240, 1190, 1030, 830, 750 cm^{-1} .

7-(4-Chlorobenzoyl)-7a-hydroxy-4,6-di(4-methoxyphenyl)perhydro-5-indenyl-4-chlorophenylmethanone 4 : Obtained as a mixture of stereoisomers (10%), R_f 0.3–0.35, ν_{\max} (neat) 3440, 1680, 1580, 1510, 1250, 1180, 1090, 1030, 830 cm^{-1} .

Reaction of 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-(2-oxocyclopentyl)-3-phenyl-1-propanone 3d with cyclopentanone 2 : Following the general procedure, the reaction of 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-(2-oxocyclopentyl)-3-phenyl-1-propanone (**3d**; 32 mg, 0.1 mmol) and cyclopentanone **2** (10 mg, 0.12 mmol) in the presence of freshly activated barium hydroxide (20 mg) in absolute alcohol (1 ml) for 12 h at RT resulted only bicyclic alcohol **4b** (12%) which was purified by column chroma-

tography using silica gel (100–200 mesh) with hexane/ethyl acetate solutions as eluent (85 : 15).

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